

Transport and Mechanical Properties of Tumor Interstitium

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Tumor interstitium is a polyelectrolyte gel composed of a collagen network and glycosaminoglycans (GAGs). The interstitial matrix blocks nanotherapeutics and leads to the heterogeneous distribution of drugs. Meanwhile, it contributes to the residual stresses which compress blood vessels and limit perfusion. Both the transport and mechanical properties of tumor interstitium are responsible for the modest nanomedicine treatment outcome. In view of this, matrix normalization (i.e. degradation of tumor matrix) has been suggested as a strategy for advancing nanomedicine. A general poroelastic theory is established to study the transport, deformation and degradation of tumor interstitium. Generalized convection-diffusion equations and damage evolution laws are proposed to describe the drug delivery and normalization, respectively. Our results reveal the swelling capacity provides the compression resistance of interstitium. The volume fraction of the matrix components, the size and surface charges of the drug particles all affect the efficiency of drug delivery. Besides, we can simulate the drug delivery and matrix normalization processes, and provide guidance for nanomedicine design and cancer therapy.

Keywords: tumor interstitium, poroelasticity, nanomedicine, normalization